

grown in the high rainfall zone with lateritic soils (Oxisols) as a wetland, transplanted crop.

Recently rice cultivation in the arid to semiarid regions of the state was boosted with the construction of dams and a network of irrigation systems. Soils of the region are typical Vertisols, medium to deep black, having about 40–65% montmorillonitic clay, and are calcareous (pH of 8.0–9.2). Fertile soils and abundance of sunshine and irrigation water have created a good potential for rice cultivation in this nontraditional area, which is about 300,000 ha. Extension of rice cultivation to these lands during the past 4–5 years has not been successful because of the lodging habit and low fertilizer response of the tall local cultivars, and iron chlorosis encountered by the high yielding semidwarf varieties and their derivatives. In these calcareous and aerobic soils available iron is low. Submerging the soils can increase iron availability. But puddling the soil and transplanting spoil the soil structure so that the soil becomes useless for crops in

Salient features of the semidwarf mutants and local tall cultivars. Maharashtra, India.

Strain	Plant ht (cm)	Lodging score (0–4)	Days to maturity (seed to seed)	Effective tillers (no./m ²)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Local</i>					
Tuljapur 1	98	4	101	269	2.5
Jalgaon 5	115	4	104	258	2.8
Ambemohor	117	4	104	265	3.8
<i>Semidwarf mutants</i>					
A-1	78	0	105	290	3.5
A-7	81	0	108	254	3.3
A-20	90	1	106	225	3.3

the following season. Thus, a rice crop on these soils must be a drilled dryland crop.

All the semidwarf varieties and derivatives tried so far have the Dee-Geo-Woo-Gen dwarfing gene, which probably has tight linkage with the gene or genes that confer susceptibility to iron deficiency. The local tall cultivars are efficient in extracting iron from these soils, and hence do not normally show symptoms of iron chlorosis. To develop alternative sources of the dwarfing habit, the local tall cultivars were subjected to mutagenesis. Semidwarf mutants isolated

in the M₂ generation were evaluated in the M₅ along with the checks in 22.5-cm spaced rows fertilized with 80 kg N and 40 kg P₂O₅/ha. The salient features of some of the semidwarf mutants and the tall checks are presented in the table. The mutants are tolerant of iron chlorosis, are nonlodging, and have good yield potential. Preliminary indications are that they are fertilizer responsive. Experiments on the agronomic manipulation of the mutants and their evaluation on a wider scale are under progress. ■

Effect of flooding depth on nitrogen, phosphate, and potash availability and change in electrochemical behavior of puddled and unpuddled soils

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A field experiment on water management of rice was conducted at Pantnagar, India. Total nitrogen content and availability of phosphorus and potassium increased with water depth (Table 1, 2).

pH decreased slightly with increasing depth of submergence in puddled soil, but not in unpuddled soil. The specific conductance value, however, increased with depth of flooding in both puddled and unpuddled soils. No change in the specific conductance value was observed in the saturation and rainfed treatments (Table 1, 2). ■

Table 1. Effect of depth of submergence on availability of nitrogen, phosphate, and potash; and on pH and specific conductance in puddled soils. 1973 wet season, Pantnagar, India.

Depth of submergence	Total nitrogen (%)	Available nutrients (kg/ha)		soil pH	Specific conductance (mmho/cm) at 25°C
		P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O		
15 cm – 1 cm	0.156	105.5	168.2	7.5	0.65
5 cm – field capacity	0.151	99.0	165.3	7.5	0.50
1 cm – field capacity	0.149	81.7	161.8	7.7	0.45
36 cm total water use (50% of total water use)	0.147	81.7	161.9	7.7	0.45
Rainfed	0.148	81.8	161.8	7.7	0.45

Table 2. Effect of depth of submergence on availability of nitrogen, phosphate, and potash; and on soil pH and specific conductance in unpuddled soils. 1973 wet season, Pantnagar, India.^a

Depth of submergence until 21 DSE	Depth of submergence from 21 DSE to maturity	Total N (%)	Available nutrients (kg/ha)		Soil pH	Specific conductance (mmho/cm) at 25°C
			P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O		
1 cm – FC	15 cm – 1 cm	0.18	85.9	156.5	7.6	0.60
1 cm – FC	5 cm – FC	0.15	82.4	141.1	7.6	0.60
1 cm – FC	1 cm – FC	0.11	76.3	127.7	7.7	0.45
5 cm – 1 cm	15 cm – 1 cm	0.18	94.6	164.4	7.6	0.63
5 cm – 1 cm	5 cm – FC	0.16	78.8	151.2	7.6	0.50
5 cm – FC	15 cm – 1 cm	0.13	76.6	120.9	7.7	0.45
5 cm – FC	5 cm – FC	0.18	81.7	168.0	7.5	0.62
5 cm – FC	5 cm – FC	0.14	77.6	164.6	7.6	0.52
5 cm – FC	1 cm – FC	0.13	75.8	141.1	7.7	0.45

^aDSE = days after seedling establishment, FC = field capacity.